

Citizen Observatory Description Template

WeObserve is a Coordination and Support Action project (2017-2021) to consolidate knowledge and share impact stories of Citizen Observatories.

This template was developed for the purposes of producing the WeObserve Citizen Observatories Landscape Report, which described and mapped a selected range of existing CO initiatives and their relevant communities and interactions. The final report can be found in the WeObserve Zenodo Repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/4472670>

Citizen Observatories are community-based environmental monitoring initiatives that invite the public to contribute observations, data and information in complement to authoritative, traditional in-situ and remote sensing Earth Observation data.

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Descriptive Metadata for Citizen Observatories

In order to align and be fully interoperable with citizen science platforms such as citizenscience.eu and SciStarter, we make use of the PPSR Common Conceptual Model (PPSR-CCM) metadata standard and data sharing protocol, and the European Citizen Science metadata schema for describing CS projects on their platform. The acronym PPSR stands for Public Participation in Scientific Research, and the canonical repository for PPSR-CCM can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/CitSciAssoc/DMWG-PPSR-Core>.

PPSR CCM Metadata	Database Information
Origin UID	<i>Globally Unique Identifier in the database where a project was first registered. Allows traceability of a project in multiple databases to its original registration. For example, the Grant Number assigned by the funding body.</i>
Origin Database	<i>The name of the project database where a project was first registered. Allows traceability of a project in multiple databases to its original registration. For example, the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS), which is the EC's primary source of results from projects funded by the EU's framework programmes (FP1 to Horizon 2020).</i>
PPSR CCM Metadata	Project Information
Project Name	<i>Short name or title of the project</i>
Project Aim	<i>Primary aim, goal or objective</i>
Project Science Topic	<i>Please make a selection from the PPSR Vocabulary = Agriculture & Veterinary science / Animals / Archaeology & Culture / Astronomy & Space / Biodiversity / Biogeography / Biology / Birds / Chemical sciences / Climate & Weather / Ecology & Environment / Education / Food science / Genetics / Geography / Geology & Earth science / Health & Medicine / Indigenous culture / Information & Computing sciences / Insects & pollinators / Long-term species monitoring / Ocean, Water, Marine & Terrestrial / Nature & outdoors / Natural resource management / Physics / Psychology / Science policy / Social sciences / Sound / Transportation / Other</i>
Participation Task	<i>Please indicate the nature of the participation task(s) in the scientific process of the project from the PPSR Vocabulary: "Annotation, Audio or video recording, Classification or tagging, DIY hacking/making, Data analysis, Data entry, Download software for distributed computing, Finding entities, Geolocation, Identification, Learning, Measurement, Observation, Photography, Problem</i>

	<i>solving, Sample analysis, Site selection and/or description, Specimen/sample collection, Transcription"</i>
Keywords	<i>Please provide keywords (comma separated) to aid indexing and searching for and finding projects.</i>
Activity Status	<i>Please indicate the activity status of the project using PPSR Vocabulary = Not yet started / Active / Periodically active / On hold / Completed / Abandoned / Terminated</i>
Start Date	<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>
End Date	<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>
Duration	<i>Use this alternative to the Start and End Date, when the duration is known but the dates are not yet set.</i>
Geographic Extent	<i>Please indicate the spatial scale(s) at which the project is implemented using PPSR vocabulary: Global, Macro-regional, National, Sub-national, Regional, City, Neighborhood</i>
Project Country/Countries	<i>The country(ies) in which the project takes place</i>
Location of project activities	<i>Please describe the locality of the project, in terms of where main participant activities take place, for example your backyard, fresh water sources, online etc...</i>
Project Language(s)	<i>Please indicate the main language(s) that project activities take place in</i>
Project Website	<i>Please provide the url of the website where the project is hosted</i>
Funding Program	<i>Please indicate the funding body or programme, if relevant</i>
Funding Source	<i>Please indicate the financial sponsor of the project, if relevant</i>
PPSR CCM Metadata	Contact Information
Project Host / Coordinator	<i>Name of the primary organization responsible for hosting or implementing the project</i>
Public Contact of the project	<i>Person that interested public or researchers should contact</i>
Public Contact Email	<i>Public contact email address</i>
Project Website	<i>Please provide the url of the website where the project is hosted</i>
PPSR CCM Metadata	Profile Information
Image	<i>An image to represent the project (url to jpeg or png file)</i>

Image Credit	<i>A credit for the image, if applicable</i>
PPSR CCM Metadata	Participation Information
How to Participate	<i>Free text description of how people can get involved in the project. Textual instructions for joining the project</i>
Project Task	<i>Free text description of the participant task(s) in the project.</i>
Intended Outcomes	<i>A set of described outcomes intended to be achieved by the project.</i>
Project Equipment	<i>Required or suggested equipment to be used in the project (e.g. monitoring tools/apps/sensor for citizen activities, online platform for visualisation of monitoring results, communication channels)</i>
Participant Links	<i>URL for links to any external resources associated with a project, such as a mobile application.</i>
PPSR CCM Metadata	Project Documentation
Link to Project Deliverables	<i>Please provide a url link to an online location where the outputs of the project can be found (such as a Zenodo or OSF repository)</i>
Link to Project Publications	<i>Please provide a url link to an online location where academic publications produced in or resulting from the project can be found (such as a project Publications page, or preprint repository)</i>

Descriptive Frameworks for Citizen Observatories

In order to investigate challenges of Awareness, Acceptability, and Sustainability that inhibit the mainstreaming of citizen science, we wished to more fully describe the nature and activities of the COs we interviewed by making use of frameworks and typologies that have been developed in the academic literature. These are summarised below, but may require more explanation to make use of the template. These explanations, along with reference to the underlying literature, can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/records/3670895>

WeObserve - Descriptive frameworks for researching & comparing Citizen Observatories	
Ranges of possibility to describe the nature of the CO within different dimensions ('Wehn's 9 dimensions')	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sensors and transmission: <i>Physical sensor</i> ↔ <i>social sensor</i> 2. Stakeholders: <i>Authorities</i> ↔ <i>citizens</i> 3. Area of application: <i>Physical environment</i> ↔ <i>human behaviour</i> 4. Purpose of citizen observatory: <i>Protect environment</i> ↔ <i>strengthen governance</i> 5. System integration: <i>Stand-alone</i> ↔ <i>integrated</i> 6. Measurement: <i>Objective</i> ↔ <i>subjective</i>

	<p>7. Implementation: <i>Bottom up</i> ↔ <i>top-down</i></p> <p>8. Communications paradigm: <i>Uni-directional</i> ↔ <i>interactive</i></p> <p>9. Citizen participation in governance processes: <i>Implicit data provision</i> ↔ <i>technical expertise</i>; <i>Individual education</i> ↔ <i>direct authority</i></p>
Monitoring Parameters (<i>'Liu's 6 Properties'</i>)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>"The aim / purpose of each programme,</i> 2. <i>its geographic scope,</i> 3. <i>project duration,</i> 4. <i>target groups,</i> 5. <i>monitoring parameters, and</i> 6. <i>data collection and interpretation, visualization and information dissemination technologies."</i>
Types of Monitoring Activities (<i>'Conrad & Hilchey's 3+3 Types of Monitoring Activities'</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Status assessment (i.e., population monitoring),</i> • <i>Impact assessment (i.e., effect of pollution), or</i> • <i>Adaptive management (i.e., managing based on monitoring);</i> • <i>Ecosystem composition (i.e., indicator species or species at risk),</i> • <i>Structure (i.e., biodiversity analysis, keystone species, predator-prey relations),</i> • <i>Processes (i.e., linking species with environment, nutrient cycling, etc.).</i>
Model of CO (<i>'Shirk's 5 Project Models'</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Contractual projects - where communities ask professional researchers to conduct a specific scientific investigation and report on the results;</i> • <i>Contributory projects - which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data;</i> • <i>Collaborative projects - which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public contribute data but also help to refine project design, analyze data, and/or disseminate findings;</i> • <i>Co-Created projects - which are designed by scientists and members of the public working together and for which at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most or all aspects of the research process; and</i> • <i>Collegial contributions - where non-credentialed individuals conduct research independently with varying degrees of expected recognition by institutionalized science and/or professional</i>
Type of CO (<i>'Wiggins & Crowston's 5 Types'</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Action - Action-oriented citizen science projects encourage participant intervention in local concerns, using scientific research as a tool to support civic agendas. They are most commonly grassroots or "bottom-up", are not conceived or</i>

	<p><i>planned by scientists, and usually involve long-term engagement in local environmental concerns.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Conservation - Conservation projects support stewardship and natural resource management goals, primarily in the area of ecology; they engage citizens as a matter of practicality and outreach, and they tend to be regional in scope.</i> ● <i>Investigation - Investigation projects are focused on scientific research goals requiring data collection from the physical environment. Education is frequently a strongly valued but unstated purpose, and task structures often support ongoing learning. These projects range from regional to international in scope, and can achieve very large scales of participation.</i> ● <i>Virtual - Science-oriented Virtual projects are ICT-mediated with no physical elements whatsoever, they are formed through top-down organizing by academics, and most projects' affiliations are exclusively academic.</i> ● <i>Education - Education projects make education and outreach their primary goals, with relevant aspects of place. They can be split into those focusing on informal versus formal learning opportunities, and are sometimes explicitly designed to permit cumulative learning experiences.</i>
<p>Domain of Application <i>('Pallacin-Silva's 8 Domains of Application' + 2)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>City Management;</i> ● <i>Species Monitoring;</i> ● <i>Water, streams, snow, sea;</i> ● <i>Biodiversity monitoring;</i> ● <i>Air and spectrum monitoring;</i> ● <i>Tools for creating monitoring projects;</i> ● <i>Global monitoring;</i> ● <i>Disaster Monitoring;</i> ● <i>Land-use Monitoring;</i> ● <i>Commodity-based Monitoring</i>
<p>Level of Geography <i>('Haklay's 3 Policy Dimensions')</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Local community;</i> ● <i>City level;</i> ● <i>Regional level;</i> ● <i>State/Country;</i> ● <i>Continental</i>
<p>Policy Application Area <i>('Haklay's 3 Policy Dimensions')</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Environmental monitoring and environmental decision making;</i> ● <i>Agriculture and food;</i> ● <i>Urban planning and cities;</i> ● <i>Health and medical research;</i> ● <i>Humanitarian support and development aid;</i> ● <i>Science awareness, and</i> ● <i>Support of scientific efforts</i>

<p>Level of Engagement (‘Haklay’s 3 Policy Dimensions’)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Passive Sensing - relies on participants providing a resource that they own (e.g., their phone or space in their backyard) for automatic sensing. The information that is collected through these sensors is then used by scientists for analysis</i> ● <i>Volunteer Computing - a method in which participants share their unused computing resources, on their personal computer, tablet, or smartphone, and allow scientists to run complex computer models when the device is not in use.</i> ● <i>Volunteer Thinking - participants contribute their ability to recognize patterns or analyze information that will then be used in a scientific project. Commonly, the analysis task is fairly standardized, making it easy to aggregate and compare results from different participants</i> ● <i>Environmental and Ecological Observation - focuses on monitoring environmental pollution or observations of flora and fauna</i> ● <i>Participatory Sensing - gives the participant more roles and control over the process. While many environmental and ecological observations follow data collection protocols that were designed by scientists, in participatory sensing the process is more distributed and emphasizes the active involvement of the participants in setting what will be collected and analyzed.</i> ● <i>Civic / Community science - also known as bottom-up science, is initiated and driven by a group of participants who identify a problem that is a concern for them and address it using scientific methods and tools. Within this type of activity, the problem formation, data collection, and analysis are often carried out by community members or in collaboration with scientists or established laboratories.</i>
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